

Unified network visualisation in Python

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Keywords: networks, graphs, trees, visualisation, phylogenetics, Python.

Documentation: <https://iplotx.readthedocs.io>

Development: <https://github.com/fabilab/iplotx>

Abstract

Graphs or networks are ubiquitous data structures across scientific disciplines, from social and knowledge graphs to ecological and gene networks. Network data do not naturally reside in a geometric space and can thus be difficult to visualise. Nonetheless, being able to visually inspect graphs is often important for data exploration, analysis, and interpretability. Among all graphs, visualisation of trees in particular is widespread in specific scientific areas such as evolutionary biology. At the moment, the software landscape to visualise networks and trees in Python is fragmented. I developed *iplotx*, a software package to visualise graphs and trees designed for broad compatibility with network and tree analysis libraries as input and a variety of outputs including raster and vector images and dynamic rendering on screens, for both Jupyter notebooks and GUI frameworks. *iplotx* guarantees identical network appearance independently of the package used to construct it, increasing reproducibility. *iplotx* uses a simple yet expressive declarative style hierarchy to achieve deep customisation on a per-element basis, and supports editable artistic elements, animations, input-device interactivity, and scalability up to hundreds of thousands of edges.

Introduction

Graphs or networks are mathematical structures used to encode relationships between entities including people (social networks), places (e.g. transportation networks), species (e.g. ecological networks, phylogenetic trees) and domain-specific objects (e.g.

gene regulatory networks). Visualising graphs is both important and non-trivial. Visually exploring small graphs or neighbourhoods of large ones can lead to deeper understanding of network structure and behaviour, however graphs do not mathematically inhabit a geometric space. Therefore, the exact same network can be visualised equally faithfully in multiple ways that look quite distinct. Naturally, visual nonuniqueness can (and, in my experience, routinely does) lead to confusion and interpretability issues.

In Python, one of the most popular programming languages worldwide (Carbonnelle, n.d.), multiple packages for network analysis are widely used, including *networkx* (Hagberg, Schult, and Swart 2008), *igraph* (Antonov et al. 2023), and *graph-tool* (Peixoto 2017). These libraries offer a broad spectrum of tools to load, build, edit, and analyse graphs. However, their visualisation capabilities are more limited. Post-render editing, animations, interactivity (e.g. mouse clicks), and scaling to different densities per pixels (DPI) are not or only partially supported. Even static image outputs by each library look different because of distinct styling of vertex color, shape, and size, label positioning and size, edge curvature, and so on. This ultimately limits both visual comparisons and interpretability across software stacks.

Trees are graphs often used to represent hierarchical relationships, such as animal evolution (Redelings and Holder 2017). Software libraries that specialise in or include tree analysis include ETE (Huerta-Cepas, Serra, and Bork 2016), cogent 3 (McArthur et al. 2025), Biopython (Cock et al. 2009) and scikit-bio (Team 2020). As for network analysis packages, visualisation support is limited and not standardised: visual outputs for the same tree as produced by various libraries appear different from each other.

iplotx fills two knowledge gaps: (i) Provide a general-purpose visualisation package for networks and trees with output that can be further styled, edited, animated, and interacted with, beyond the capability of current software, and (ii) Increase scientific reproducibility by guaranteeing that, given a network or tree, the same exact visual output is generated independently of the analysis library it was processed through.

Results

Network visualisation sits between network analysis and graphical rendering onto paper or screen. The goal of *iplotx* is to unify this intermediate stage for the Python ecosystem (**Figure 1A**). For this purpose, *iplotx* was designed from the ground up to accept input from multiple network and tree analysis libraries (Antonov et al. 2023; Hagberg, Schult, and Swart 2008; McArthur et al. 2025; Team 2020; Huerta-Cepas, Serra, and Bork 2016; Cock et al. 2009). At runtime, *iplotx* also scans the Python installation for any additional package declaring itself as an input data provider. This mechanism enables

external developers to independently add compatibility with *iplotx* to their package. After ingestion, data from all input providers is represented internally in the same exact way, guaranteeing the same visual output independently of the input stream. This extends to future providers that are not currently compatible with *iplotx*, such as *graph-tool* (Peixoto 2017). *iplotx* also implements simple network and tree data structures for users wishing to eschew external package dependencies.

Consistent output on multiple rendering backends was achieved through tight integration with *Matplotlib* (Hunter 2007), a popular library for data plotting that can export charts into multiple vector and raster formats (e.g. PNG, SVG) but also offers interactive renderers such as Tkinter, Qt, and GTK, which react to mouse and keyboard events and can be animated (**Figure 1A**). *iplotx* implements a hierarchy of Matplotlib artists to represent visual elements including vertices, edges, arrows, and labels (**Figure 1B**), with additional elements, such as cascades and leaf edges, available for trees specifically (**Figure 1C**). This object-oriented approach facilitates live editing of plot artists, animations, and interactive behaviour (e.g. HTML buttons). *iplotx* objects can be combined with other artists such as bar, line, and scatter plots, images, and inset axes. *iplotx* visualisations are compatible with seaborn (Waskom et al. 2014), pandas (McKinney 2011), scipy (Virtanen et al. 2020), and other Matplotlib-using packages.

In addition to broad interoperability, *iplotx* was designed around a simple yet expressive declarative styling hierarchy (**Figure 1D**). The internal style library can be complemented by custom style dictionaries. Styles can be combined, moreover partially specified styles are accepted and automatically equipped with reasonable fallbacks. For maximum flexibility, most style leaf properties (e.g. vertex size) can be expressed in three distinct ways: (1) A constant for all elements of that kind, (2) A list or sequence that will cycle through the elements of that kind, or (3) A mapping from each element to its visual property (e.g. a dictionary from vertices to sizes). This styling capabilities also enable unique features such as partially angular trees, custom padding from a vertex border, and edge waypoints and offsets.

Although visualisation of very large networks is intrinsically challenging due to pixel density and limitations of the human brain, *iplotx* can visualise networks with hundreds of thousands of nodes and edges within seconds on a modern laptop (**Figure 1E**). Empirical tests estimate the runtime complexity as $O(n + m)$, where n and m are the number of nodes and edges, an expected result since the backend needs to render vertices and edges individually.

iplotx follows best practices in free open-source software development. The codebase is versioned, documentation including a gallery of about 50 examples, continuous

integration/development pipelines are in place, 180 unit tests cover 94% of the codebase, code formatting tools and pre-commit hooks ensure high readability, and user and contributor interactions take place online transparently and respectfully.

Acknowledgements

My sincere thanks to Thomas Caswell (Matplotlib), Dan Schult and the networkx development team, Tamás Nepusz and Vincent Traag (igraph), Gavin Huttley (cogent3), and Peter Cock (biopython) for scientific discussions and design suggestions. *iploTx* was initially designed during a short residency at CIBIO, University of Trento, Italy graciously hosted by Maria Caterina Mione and Nicola Segata.

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Figures

Figure 1: iplotx implements a unified interface to network and tree visualisation. **A)** Schematic representation of network visualisation workflows with *iplotx* as a universal intermediate stage. **B)** Plotting elements of network visualisations in *iplotx*. **C)** Additional plotting elements of tree visualisations. **D)** Style hierarchy and options for individual style properties or leaves. **E)** Runtime scalability for Erdős–Rényi graphs with varying number of nodes (n) and edges (m). Black stars indicate graphs with twice as many edges as nodes. All computations were performed on a modern laptop.